

Integrating social vulnerability into food fraud vulnerability assessment: policy implications for authenticity in Spanish honey

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ABSTRACT

Cooperation on food fraud in the EU has become more structured since the establishment of the EU Food Fraud Network in 2013, with honey at the centre of recent regulatory changes regarding labelling and control measures. Despite progress, social vulnerability considerations have been largely overlooked in existing policy and academic discussions. Through narrative analysis of interviews with experts and actors from the Spanish honey value chain and European institutions, we explore nested layers of food fraud vulnerability: product and supply chain-related food fraud vulnerabilities, social vulnerabilities, institutional vulnerabilities, and vulnerabilities related to international trade and market dynamics. Particular emphasis is placed on understanding how these dynamics affect vulnerable actors and limit their ability to respond to fraud. In a sector dominated by small and medium-sized beekeepers, food fraud poses a major threat to the viability of beekeeping. Key vulnerabilities include regulatory gaps, inconsistent detection methods, and global trade pressures that disproportionately affect vulnerable value chain actors. In particular, we highlight social vulnerability factors like low participation in decision-making, and unequal distribution of fraud-related risks and responsibilities throughout the value chain, which undermine trust between actors. Beekeepers and their associations advocate for geographical indication (GI) schemes, direct trade, and short supply chains to reduce fraud risks, address power imbalances, and improve traceability and authenticity. This research highlights the need for regulatory frameworks that promote equity, transparency, and fair risk sharing. It contributes to embedding social vulnerability into food fraud vulnerability concepts and advocates for socially responsible governance that prioritizes the rights and resilience of all actors within the agri-food system.

1. Introduction

Since the creation of the EU Food Fraud Network in 2013, cooperation between Member States on food fraud issues has been increasingly structured and coordinated (European Union, 2020). Food fraud has been defined as a form of non-compliance involving deliberate deceptive actions in the food supply chain where businesses or individuals intentionally mislead customers to gain unfair advantages (Winkler et al., 2023).¹ Since 2019, Member States have been required to carry out risk-based controls to detect fraudulent and deceptive practices in agri-food chains (Winkler et al., 2023). Despite ongoing efforts, the true scope of food fraud remains largely elusive, with its full extent still unknown. Its complex and cross-border nature as a social phenomenon is gaining increasing recognition, underscoring the challenges of understanding

and addressing this global issue, which carries significant social, economic, and environmental consequences. Since the introduction of the food fraud vulnerability approach for industry, the concept of vulnerability has become central to both the academic literature and food fraud prevention systems (Spink & Moyer, 2011; Manning et al., 2016; van Ruth et al., 2017). In the context of food fraud, several scholars highlight food fraud vulnerability as the susceptibility to a [given] risk (van Ruth et al., 2017; Manning & Soon, 2019). Food fraud vulnerability has been explored following different approaches, primarily based on criminology and behavioural science theories (e.g., Spink & Moyer, 2011; Manning et al., 2016; van Ruth et al., 2017; van Ruth, 2019). In this context, key food fraud vulnerability elements include opportunities (e.g., technical opportunities such as product characteristics and availability of detection methods), motivations (e.g., economic factors such

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¹ Commission Regulation (EU) 2019/1715 defines agri-food fraud as “a non-compliance concerning any suspected intentional action by businesses or individuals, for the purpose of deceiving purchasers and gaining undue advantage therefrom, in violation of the rules referred to in Article 1(2) of Regulation (EU) 2017/625”.

as price differences between countries and behaviour drivers such as ethical business culture) and control measure-related factors (van Ruth et al., 2017, p.71). Based on this food fraud vulnerability understanding, the Safe Supply of Affordable Food Everywhere (SSAFE) tool was developed (van Ruth et al., 2017). The tool can be applied along the food supply chain, from animal feed and primary production to manufacturing and catering, at the ingredient, product, brand, facility, country, or company level (SSAFE, 2015). Other food fraud vulnerability assessment tools include the USP's Food Fraud Mitigation Guidance, the IFS Standards Product Fraud and EMAAlert – Economically Motivated Adulteration – Vulnerability Assessment Tool (see Manning & Soon, 2019; Barrere et al., 2020 for reviews of these tools). Drawing on this literature, several studies have advanced knowledge on food fraud opportunities, motivations, and control measures. These studies have also highlighted different levels of food fraud vulnerability according to supply chains and their tiers, using the SSAFE tool for several food supply chains, and focusing on diverse supply chain actors such as producers, business-to-business (B2B) companies, food manufacturers and retailers (e.g., van Ruth et al., 2018; Yan et al., 2020). In the last decade, work on food fraud prevention has expanded to include root cause analysis, informed by behavioural and social science perspectives (McElwee et al., 2017; Spink, 2019).

Fraudulent activities are enabled by a number of factors such as asymmetric information, imperfect certification processes, and weak monitoring and enforcement systems (Meerza et al., 2019; Giannakas & Yiannaka, 2023). In honey, fraud severity is exacerbated by increasing scarcity of natural honey, rapidly evolving adulteration methods that outpace official detection capabilities, and growing profit opportunities associated with fraudulent practices (García & Schwarzingler, 2021). In particular, gaps in detection and enforcement remain critical concerns (please see Section 2 for more detail).

Economic analyses have identified asymmetric information, often rooted in underlying power imbalances, as a central issue underlying food fraud, with significant negative effects on both consumer welfare and industry profits (Ehmke et al., 2019). This focus on information and power asymmetries aligns with broader trends in agri-food systems, where increasing corporate concentration and control has contributed to widening inequalities (Clapp & Purugganan, 2020), creating what Lang et al. (2023, p.1) describe as “new winners and losers”. Within this context, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) often face inequitable access to food fraud information and struggle to implement effective mitigation and prevention strategies, as many widely recognised systems require resources more accessible to large enterprises (Manning & Soon, 2019; Popping et al., 2022), placing them at a competitive disadvantage. Beekeeper associations, consumer protection groups, and grassroots organisations have raised concerns regarding the uneven impacts of fraud, as observed in the honey sector, evidenced by several beekeepers' mobilisations against “massive” imports of fake honey (ECVC, 2025). Weak enforcement and insufficient market oversight allow fraudulent actors to operate with minimal consequences, placing additional strain on smaller producers who must compete in distorted markets without adequate protection (Bruneau et al., 2025).

Despite these vulnerabilities across the value chains, assessments of societal welfare in food fraud contexts have predominantly centred on consumer welfare (see Bimbo et al., 2019; Charlebois et al., 2016), while largely overlooking other food fraud consequences. In particular, discussions of social vulnerabilities, such as low participation in decision-making processes and unequal distribution of fraud-related risks and responsibilities across value chains, remain limited in both academic research and policy development on food fraud.

Social vulnerabilities fundamentally shape the landscape of decision-making and should therefore be central to decision-making and adaptive action (Adger, 2006). Including social vulnerability analysis in political decisions on food fraud would contribute to achieving key social justice goals of the European food policy.

This study seeks to address this gap by moving beyond perspectives

limited to criminal behaviour and industry-centred approaches. Through narrative analysis, we aim to nuance the concept of vulnerability to food fraud by drawing on the broader concept of social vulnerability. Social vulnerabilities are constructed by the social, economic, political and cultural factors that shape the susceptibility of different groups to harm and influence their capacity to respond (Cutter, 2024). Following Wisner (2016), we examine the key factors and characteristics that make individuals and groups vulnerable to fraud, while restricting their ability to anticipate, cope with, and recover from it.

This study is based on in-depth interviews with experts and value chain actors within the Spanish honey value chain, considering both honey marketed under geographical indication (GI) schemes and honey produced and marketed without GI designation. In addition, we conducted interviews with experts at the level of European and international organisations. First, we examine social vulnerability concepts and their applicability to food fraud vulnerability. Second, following a narrative approach we: (a) identify factors that increase vulnerability to food fraud in the honey value chain; (b) understand actors' perceptions of vulnerability and how food fraud affects them; and (c) analyse the measures and adaptations implemented by different actors and their proposed remedies. The discussion section of this article is structured around two key levels. At the conceptual level, we build on and refine the concept of food fraud vulnerability, introducing additional nuances, while emphasising the need to expand current food fraud vulnerability assessments. At the policy level, we advocate for the integration of social vulnerability as a fundamental priority within regulatory frameworks to ensure that food systems are not only safe, but also equitable and fair. This can be achieved through improved analysis of social vulnerabilities to better inform policy decisions.

1.1. Social vulnerability concepts

The concept of vulnerability in the context of environmental and social change is broad, encompassing various fields such as risk management, sociology, psychology, and environmental studies. Important factors of the vulnerability concept include the degree to which a system, individual, or community is exposed to a hazard or threat (exposure), the extent to which a system, community, or individual is likely to be affected by exposure to a threat or hazard (sensitivity) (see, e.g., Cutter et al., 2003), and the ability of a system, community, or individual to adjust, respond, or recover from exposure to threats or hazard (adaptive capacity) (see e.g. Smit & Wandel 2006; Adger, 2006).

In food fraud studies, the concept of vulnerability refers to the susceptibility of a food supply chain or its components to fraudulent activities (van Ruth et al., 2017; Manning & Soon, 2019). The concept of vulnerability is often assessed using tools like the SSAFE, whose conceptual roots are based on routine activities theory (Cohen & Felson, 1979). The theory, as translated to food fraud, considers three key drivers: opportunities (suitable target), motivations (motivated offender), and control measures (van Ruth et al., 2017). The complexity of the food supply chain, e.g., the number of intermediaries or lack of direct control and the type of food, facilitates adulteration or the ability to detect fraud. For instance, certain food products are more susceptible to fraud due to their high value; examples include olive oil, honey, seafood, and spices (see e.g., Han et al., 2022, Lawrence et al., 2024).

While extensive research has examined vulnerability to food fraud in food supply chains, focusing on product quality, control systems and regulatory oversight, consumer protection, and approaches to counter adulteration (see, for example, Manning & Soon, 2014), understanding of social vulnerability remains limited.

Social vulnerabilities are generally complex and challenging to quantify. They often arise from social factors that shape the susceptibility of different groups to harm and influence their capacity to respond (Cutter, 2024). Additionally, these vulnerabilities are affected by place-based inequalities, which encompass the characteristics of communities and the built environment (Cutter et al., 2003). Social vulnerability is

the product of the past social, economic, political, environmental, and cultural processes affecting human systems, while hazard-related events limit the capacity to cope, eventually leading to significant social impacts and losses (Cutter, 2024). Social vulnerability is a dynamic process; for instance, social processes that influence people's lives increasingly cross territorial borders, leading to new vulnerabilities to transnational forces (Fraser, 2007). Based on Wisner's (2016) definition, vulnerable individuals or groups are those particularly susceptible to harm due to a combination of factors that limit their ability to anticipate, cope with, and recover from adverse situations. These factors may include socio-economic, political or environmental conditions that weaken their resilience. Vulnerability is defined not only by exposure to risks, but also by systemic responses such as inadequate support systems, lack of resources or ineffective policies that further limit an individual's or a group's ability to mitigate or overcome challenges (Bergstrand, et al., 2015).

In the context of food fraud, it is crucial to identify which value chain actors are most vulnerable, how they are disproportionately affected by fraudulent activities, and the conditions that heighten the vulnerability of both the chain and its actors, considering the role of various environmental, social, and political factors. For example, fraudulent activities have been identified as a major cause of significant human rights and environmental risks in the honey supply chain, emphasizing social justice as an imperative to prevent and address unfair trade practices (Fairtrade International, 2023). Fairtrade's (2023) risk assessments show that activities such as adulteration, mislabelling and smuggling distort market dynamics, leading to declining returns for small-scale producers and contributing to income insecurity in violation of their right to an adequate livelihood and decent working conditions. Furthermore, food fraud disproportionately affects vulnerable groups, including women-headed households, by endangering a vital source of income and exacerbating existing gender-based barriers to economic participation and access to resources (Fairtrade International, 2023).

However, there is still a need for more in-depth research on vulnerability to food fraud in relation to social factors, such as participation, equity in decision-making, and equity in responsibilities and distribution of risks and consequences of food fraud throughout the food value chain.

2. Background information

2.1. The EU honey sector and its food fraud vulnerabilities

The EU is the world's second-largest honey producer, following China, with a total production of approximately 286,000 tonnes in 2022 (European Union, 2024a). Major honey-producing countries within the EU include Germany (34,100 tonnes), France (31,400 tonnes), Rumania (28,800 tonnes), Spain (27,400 tonnes), Hungary (25,000 tonnes), and Poland (24,000 tonnes) (European Union, 2024a). Despite significant domestic production, the EU is a major net importer of honey, sourcing around 163,700 tonnes from non-EU countries in 2023, valued at €359.3 million (Eurostat, 2024). Key suppliers are China (37 % of imports with an average unit value of imported honey of €1.39/kg), Ukraine (28 % of imports with an average unit value of imported honey of €2.07/kg), and Argentina (12 % of imports with an average unit value of imported honey of €2.37/kg) (European Union, 2024a). The EU exported 24,900 tonnes of honey in 2023, mainly to the United Kingdom, Saudi Arabia, and Switzerland (Eurostat, 2024). The EU's honey self-sufficiency rate stands at 63 %, resulting in a largely negative trade balance for the sector (European Union, 2024a). Most of the imported honey is used in blends (about 80 %, according to information from the European Federation of Honey Packers and Distributors FEEDM, cited in European Union, 2023a). Approximately 30 % of all EU honey is marketed directly by beekeepers to consumers, while 70 % is marketed in retail and industry under brand names (FEEDM, 2024).

The European honey value chain exhibits distinct structural

characteristics across its nodes. At the production node, the sector is characterised by fragmentation and small-scale operations, with approximately 615,000 beekeepers managing around 19 million beehives across the European Union as of 2020 (European Union, 2022). The majority of these beekeepers operate fewer than 150 beehives, the common threshold for professional production, further emphasizing the disaggregated nature of this upstream node (European Union, 2024a). In contrast, the mid-stream and down-stream nodes of the value chain show substantial concentration, with only a few major importers operating in each country. A 2015 study shows that a few major importers typically handle packaging for three primary distribution channels: large retailers (which account for 50–60 % of honey distribution), industrial processing (20–30 %), and wholesalers (10–30 %) (CBI, 2015). At the retail node, a dozen large supermarket and hypermarket chains dominate honey distribution to consumers, wielding considerable bargaining power within the value chain due to their operational scale and market position (CBI, 2015). More recent analyses have reached similar conclusions, highlighting the concentration of the honey trade and packaging among a small number of major importers in key European markets such as Germany, the UK, France and Belgium. Many of these importers also serve as re-export hubs (CBI, 2024).

The European honey sector faces several challenges, including declining bee populations due to diseases like the *Varroa* spp. mite, extensive use of chemicals and pesticides in agriculture, and other factors such as climate change (Van Espen et al., 2023). In addition, market competition and price pressure further complicate the situation (European Union, 2024a; Bruneau et al., 2025). Several organisations such as producer organisations and consumer protection associations, have identified honey fraud as a significant threat to the viability of apiculture both in Europe and globally, have expressed concern about the scale of fraud, and called for appropriate investigations and methods revisions (see e.g., Apimondia, 2019; COAG, 2021; Kragl, 2021; Food-watch, 2023).

A coordinated control plan organised in 2015–2017 at the EU level, as well as in Norway and Switzerland, showed that at least 14 % of the samples tested did not conform to purity benchmarks, both for honey produced in the EU and for honey imported from third countries (Aries et al., 2016). Following this investigation, an EU coordinated action, "From the Hives", was initiated in 2021 to assess the incidence of non-conforming honey imported into the EU (European Union, 2023a). This action – coordinated by the Directorate General for Health and Food Safety (DG SANTE) and implemented by the members of the EU Agri-Food Fraud Network (FFN) with analytical assistance from the Joint Research Center (JRC) and investigation support from European Anti-fraud Office (OLAF) – confirmed that a significant portion of honey imported into the EU is suspected of not complying with the provisions of the "Honey Directive" (46 % based on 320 samples). Most importantly, the investigation shows improved detection capability compared to previous studies due to the use of a set of methods with improved detection capability (JRC methodology)² (Ždiniaková et al., 2023). While there are analytical methods available to verify honey authenticity, they are currently insufficiently sensitive to detect low-to-moderate levels of sugar adulteration (Ždiniaková et al., 2023). As a result, fraudsters adapt their adulteration practices to stay below the detection limits of these methods. Despite new investigations into the addition of sugar syrup, various forms of honey fraud, including those involving filtration, thermal treatment, water content, and mislabelling of geographical, botanical origin, remain a global concern (Soares et al., 2017; Apimondia, 2019), and the full extent of honey fraud and its consequences remain unclear. The Directive 2001/110/EC particularly establishes that no pollen or other individual honey ingredient is to be

² The so-called JRC methodology refers to a set of methods with improved detection capabilities compared to the methods used in previous coordinated actions (see Ždiniaková et al., 2023 for a detailed description of the methods).

removed, unless that is inevitable when organic and inorganic foreign materials are removed. That process may be carried out by filtering. Where such filtering leads to the removal of a significant quantity of pollen, the consumer must be correctly informed to that effect by means of an appropriate indication on the label (Council of the European Union, 2002). Numerous organisations have raised concerns about current production practices and called for stricter adherence to the CA Codex Alimentarius Commission (1981) standard of honey and to its description of essential composition and quality factors, which specifies that honey should not be heated or processed to such an extent that its essential composition is changed and/or its quality impaired. They argue that practices such as ultrafiltration, premature harvesting, and technical manipulation compromise the integrity of honey and mislead consumers. These concerns, along with the specific provisions and related non-compliant practices, are summarised in Table 1. Table 1 further elaborate on the EU Honey Directive 2001/110-defined criteria that honey must meet to be considered and sold as “honey”, and the cases considered not to meet the Directive’s criteria, as elaborated by Bruneau et al. (2025).

Honey is currently central to changes in European regulation mostly related to labelling and strengthening controls, with numerous organisations demanding harmonised and improved detection methods and stronger import controls (see e.g. Foodwatch., 2023). In 2024, political agreement was reached by the European Parliament and Council to strengthen the existing marketing standards applicable to honey amidst the so-called Breakfast Directive,³ specifically concerning common rules on detailed origin labelling and methods harmonisation (European Commission, 2024a). Agreement was reached that honey labels must list countries of origin in descending order of percentage, with flexibility for Member States to require percentages for only the top four if they exceed 50 % of the blend. The Commission is empowered to introduce harmonised methods to detect adulteration, to trace the origin of honey and to verify that it has not been overheated, that pollen has not been removed from honey and that methods are in place to trace the geographical origin of honey before it reaches the consumer (European Commission, 2024a, see also European Commission, 2023).

3. Methods

3.1. Data and data analysis

We investigated the vulnerability to food fraud in the Spanish honey value chain, considering both honey marketed under a geographical indication (GI) scheme and honey produced and marketed without GI designation. Using a narrative analysis approach, we conducted in-depth interviews with a total of 22 participants, including 7 experts from Spain and European organisations and 15 honey value chain actors in Spain. The actors represented a variety of sectors: government, including one certification initiative (2), beekeepers (2), producers and packers (4), representatives of producer and packer organisations (2), retailers and traders (2), and producer and consumer protection organisations (3). It is worth noting that many of these roles overlap. For example, some beekeepers also package honey and represent producer organisations; and some packers engage in importing.

Participants were selected using snowball sampling, whereby research participants are asked to assist the research team in identifying other potential interviewees (Parker et al., 2019). A set of guiding interview questions was prepared, but flexibility maintained throughout the process to allow new aspects to emerge. The study design and research instruments were approved by the relevant institutional ethics committee. All participants provided voluntary informed consent prior to participating and all interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed. Data analysis had two stages. First, the interview transcripts were

Table 1

General Provisions Under EU Honey Directive and Codex Alimentarius Standard.

Regulatory Framework	General Provision	Cases that can be considered as not meeting the criteria of the Directive as elaborated by Bruneau et al. (2025)
EU Honey Directive 2001/110/EC	No pollen or other individual ingredient of honey is to be removed, unless that is inevitable when organic and inorganic foreign materials are removed. That process may be carried out by filtering. Where such filtering leads to the removal of a significant quantity of pollen, the consumer must be correctly informed to that effect by means of an appropriate indication on the label.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addition of sugar syrup or any other elements (enzymes, pollens, dyes, etc.) whether during nectar flow, post-harvest treatments or blending. • Harvesting of un-ripened honey. • Filtering using resins to retain certain undesirable elements such as antibiotics or, more simply, filters that significantly remove pollen without mentioning it.* • Incorrect geographical and/or botanical origin. • Significant degradation of enzymes naturally present in honey. • Excess HMF (hydroxymethylfurfural).
Standard	General Provision	Modes of honey production that do not comply with the Codex Alimentarius Standard as elaborated by Apimondia (2019).
Codex Alimentarius (1981) revised in 1987, 2001; amended in 2019, 2022.	3.1 Honey sold as such shall not have added to it any food ingredient, including food additives, nor shall any other additions be made other than honey. Honey shall not have any objectionable matter, flavour, aroma, or taint absorbed from foreign matter during its processing and storage. The honey shall not have begun to ferment or effervesce. No pollen or constituent particular to honey may be removed except where this is unavoidable in the removal of foreign inorganic or organic matter. 3.2 Honey shall not be heated or processed to such an extent that its essential composition is changed and/or its quality is impaired. 3.3 Chemical or biochemical treatments shall not be used to influence honey crystallization.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One-box Langstroth-type beehive during honey crop. • Harvesting of immature honey by the beekeeper. • Honey dehydration with technical devices, such as vacuum dryers. • Use of Ion-Exchange Resins to remove residues and lighten the colour of honey. • Feeding bees during a nectar flow.

* Filtered honey will be taken back as “honey intended for the industry” following a recent amendment to the Honey Directive (2024).

³ The revised Honey Directive (2001/110) came into force on 13 June 2024.

analysed inductively, with an initial coding that grouped similar conceptual data under common headings, which were then further organised into broader categories. During this process, we identified vulnerability concepts directly from the collected data instead of relying on predefined categories. In the second step, following Entman (1993), narrative analysis identified problem definitions, causal interpretations, moral evaluations, and treatment recommendations related to food fraud. Narrative analysis uncovers the framing of concepts underlying particular communication. Framing refers to how communicators (consciously or unconsciously) select certain aspects of a perceived reality and make them more salient in their communication to promote a particular problem definition, causal interpretation, moral evaluation, and/or treatment recommendation for the issue described (Entman, 1993). This type of discursive analysis enables understanding of social, technological, economic and political processes particularly relevant for policy interventions that inevitably provide legitimisation and authority for preferred narratives and interests (Scoones et al., 2019). While interview data served as the primary source for our analysis, interview narratives were factually cross-checked against additional sources, including policy documents, news articles, and reports. The findings were then discussed alongside existing literature on food fraud vulnerability and social vulnerability in agri-food value chains, and the research findings' contribution to international food policy debates. In this article, to preserve fidelity, we present the findings in narrative form, incorporating edited quotes from the raw data that accurately reflect participant voices (see Section 4).

3.2. Case study

Beekeeping represents an important economic sector in Spain; 36,833 production units were recorded in 2024 (MAPA, 2025). Of these, 17 % are managed by beekeepers operating more than 150 hives (MAPA, 2025). Approximately 3 million beehives were recorded in Spain in 2023, representing 14 % of the total number of beehives in Europe and making Spain the leading country in terms of share of beehives (European Union, 2024a). However, the number of hives decreased by about 4 % compared to 2022 (European Union, 2024a). Moreover, honey production has shown a downward trend, with a notable 19.5 % decrease in 2023 compared to 2021 levels, attributed to various factors such as weather conditions, high colony mortality, changes in agricultural practices, and disease (MAPA, 2025). In 2024, however, production returned to levels comparable to those observed in 2021 (MAPA, 2025). Beekeeping in the north and north-west is characterised by a high number of beekeepers that operate less than 150 hives, most of whom do not practise transhumance,⁴ whereas beekeeping in the centre and south/south-east is characterised by a higher degree of professionalisation and is mostly transhumant (MAPA, 2025). Within Spain's honey value chain, packaging and distribution nodes exhibit significant concentration. Despite hundreds of registered companies (RGSEAA, 2025),⁵ a dozen major operators (packaging and distribution companies) collectively represent nearly 90 % of the market value, according to industry associations such as ASEMIEL-ANIMPA.⁶ Despite this downstream concentration, the value chain maintains diversification through hundreds of small beekeeping operations that vertically

integrate packaging and distribution functions, creating alternative value chain pathways directly to consumers.⁶ The chain's import node demonstrates similar concentration; despite hundreds of registered companies, a limited number of firms dominate honey imports into the Spanish market (RGSEAA, 2025).

According to the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food, Spain imported 35,572 tonnes of honey (accumulated volume) in 2024 while exporting 26,942 tonnes during the same period (MAPA, 2025). The main destinations for Spanish honey exports were primarily European Union countries, specifically France, Germany, Italy, and Portugal (MAPA, 2025). Some non-EU destinations included Saudi Arabia, the United Kingdom, the United States, and Switzerland, though these represented relatively small volumes (MAPA, 2025). The year 2023 marked a significant shift in import patterns as non-EU imports exceeded EU imports by volume for the first time (MAPA, 2024). Despite this trend, Portugal remained Spain's largest source of honey imports with 8,056 tonnes in 2023 (MAPA, 2024). For non-EU suppliers, Argentina led with 5,811 tonnes, while Chinese imports notably decreased from 8,124 tonnes in 2022 to 5,373 tonnes in 2023 (MAPA, 2024). Analysis by COAG (2024), based on DataComex data, identified a pattern of honey triangulation through Portugal, with Portuguese operators selling 9,657 tonnes to Spain in 2024 at €1.60/kg while simultaneously buying 7,444 tonnes from China at €1.13/kg and 1,421 tonnes from India at €1.54/kg (COAG, 2024). China maintained its position as the second-largest direct supplier to Spain, providing 6,527 tonnes (18 % of total imports) at a price of €1.17/kg (COAG, 2024). Other significant suppliers included Argentina (4,965 tonnes at €1.89/kg), Ukraine (4,569 tonnes at €1.89/kg), and Germany (2,890 tonnes at €2.52/kg) (COAG, 2024).

4. Results

Narrative analysis results provide insights into various levels of vulnerability to food fraud in the Spanish honey value chain, including product and supply chain-related food fraud vulnerabilities, social vulnerabilities, institutional vulnerabilities, and vulnerabilities related to international trade and market dynamics (Fig. 1 and Table 2). It is important to note that several factors presented in Fig. 1 are interlinked, with complex feedback between different elements reinforcing vulnerabilities. All vulnerability levels interact with social vulnerability, as issues like inconsistent and opaque information on trade volumes and price pressures have broader implications for how individuals or groups experience and respond to fraud, thereby increasing social vulnerability. Similarly, institutional vulnerabilities may be rooted in social aspects such as a lack of participation and equity in decision-making, or may increase the social vulnerability of already vulnerable groups. The following sections present participants' perceptions of different vulnerability levels, concluding with a description of social vulnerability in the honey value chain. This final section examines perceived consequences of food fraud for vulnerable actors, responsibilities and participation in fraud prevention and detection, and adaptation/remedial proposals provided by study participants.

4.1. Product and supply chain-related food fraud vulnerabilities

In terms of product and supply chain related vulnerabilities, our participants expressed concerns about processes altering the composition of the final product, such as harvesting immature honey, honey dehydration, ultrafiltration and flavouring processes. These processes increase the risk of food fraud as they can manipulate the composition of honey, mask adulteration and mislead consumers about authenticity. Food fraud risks mentioned by participants include dilution with different syrups, resins to remove residues and lighten the colour, and selling honey that is mislabelled or adulterated regarding its botanical or geographical origin, as well as unlabelled honey. At the production level, participants noted that vulnerability is heightened by various socio-environmental factors. These include the mass proliferation of

⁴ Transhumance in honey production is the strategic seasonal relocation of bee colonies to optimize honey yields by following flowering patterns and nectar flows across different geographical locations (Van Espen et al., 2023).

⁵ A search in the Registered Food Business Finder (RGSEAA) resulted in around 600 packing companies, 188 distribution companies, and 198 import companies registered in Spain; however, their main activity is broadly specified as companies trading or processing sugar and sugar derivatives, honey, and products related to honey production.

⁶ Personal communication with Spanish honey traders and packers' association ASEMIEL-ANIMPA.

Fig. 1. Multi-level nested vulnerabilities in the honey value chain, based on coding scheme from interviews, author's elaboration.

hives, reduced hive productivity, and increased colony mortality. These challenges are perceived as interlinked, stemming from issues like climate change, pests, and diseases, which all contribute to the decline in natural honey production. Beekeepers are particularly concerned because climatic factors act as stressors for bees, leading to changes in bee behaviour and reproduction. Climate change has a significant impact on flowering periods, leading to reduced nectar production and consequently honey production, as this participant explains:

In Spain we have an almost structural problem of drought in certain areas. This is causing an alarming drop in honey production yields, and in (name of organisation) we have very professional producers from a technical point of view, who carry out impeccable management with very respectful techniques in the hives. Although they (beekeepers) do everything in the most respectful way with the hive and use as few chemicals as possible, they do not get the necessary blooms for the hive to produce honey that gives them a sufficient economic return. (ID12, representative of a producer organisation)

This situation is combined with a number of invasive species of concern for beekeepers such as the *Vespa velutina* and pests such as the *Varroa* spp. mite and increasing production costs as reflected by this Asturian participant:

...The cost of production in Asturias is very high, especially because we have very low production averages per hive. We have an average of 10, 12 kilos per hive. In the end, the cost of production for each kilo that we put on the market is very high for us, and the cost of distribution is also high... and in the end, this honey, which can be fraudulent or mislabelled, enters through distribution channels with much lower costs and, above all, with honeys from areas where the hives are very large, even where there is large transhumance and the hives produce in 3 or 4 blooms a year... they are competitors... We compare different ways of beekeeping and honey production... This makes us go to the market with different production costs and fight to maintain the highest quality honeys while trying to convince the end customer of this price differentiation. (ID04, beekeeper and packer).

High production and distribution costs make it difficult for beekeepers to compete in increasingly consolidated markets, where competitiveness is influenced by price but also by the presence of potentially fraudulent or mislabelled honey from domestic and imported sources. Such practices, particularly, when associated with large-scale operations using different production methods, can distort market signals and intensify economic pressures on smaller producers. This perceived “unfair” competition contributes to social vulnerabilities in the honey value chain, especially for actors with limited capacity to adapt or absorb market shocks (see Section 4.4).

4.2. Institutional vulnerabilities related to food fraud (legislation and analytical methods)

As several participants discussed, the Honey Directive's revision is highly contested. The major concerns relate to the definition of honey and its parameters, labelling, and the regulation of certain processes such as honey filtration, honey maturation, and dehumidification, as reflected in this testimony, which highlights several layers of power dynamics within the honey industry, particularly between traditional beekeepers, industrial producers, regulators, and lobbying forces:

Honey is a product that was defined in the 60 s, so 80 years ago, with analytical methods that are practically that old and we're still fighting over it. We're dealing with things that are outdated, that don't make any sense any more, that we can cheat on. First of all, we need to do away with filtered honeys, because filtered honeys open the door to syrup. Obviously, between a well-made syrup and filtered honey, especially if it's been heated, pasteurised, etc., there's virtually no difference. There's virtually no indicator left. It's a recipe for outrageous fraud. There are lobbies that are really hell-bent against it. The problem of honey maturation... We're dealing with competitive disparities. Our production methods are not at all similar. If you produce wet nectar, you make twice as much as mature honey. After that, industrial dehumidification systems pose a problem... Two years ago, beekeepers got into a crazy dispute over dehumidification... It's always a question of small details. It takes an enormous

Table 2
Description of food fraud vulnerabilities.

Vulnerability level	Definition
Social vulnerability	Social vulnerability refers to the challenges and susceptibilities that arise from social factors, influencing how different groups experience and respond to harm. In the context of food fraud, these vulnerabilities are shaped by inequalities in participation, decision-making, and the distribution of risks and consequences across the food value chain. Institutional vulnerabilities or vulnerabilities related to non-transparent trade dynamics may amplify social vulnerability.
Product and supply chain-related food fraud vulnerabilities	Product and supply chain-related food fraud vulnerabilities refer to weaknesses in production and distribution processes that allow deliberate deception for economic gain. These vulnerabilities often include opportunities to change the composition or presentation of a product, leading to mislabelling or adulteration. For example, the marketing of honey primarily as a blend increases the risk of fraud. Vulnerabilities also arise from socio-ecological factors affecting production, including reduced productivity, environmental stressors and escalating costs. Together, these factors contribute to an increased risk of fraudulent practices as producers face greater difficulties in meeting market demands.
Institutional vulnerabilities related to food fraud (legislation and analytical methods)	Institutional vulnerabilities refer to weaknesses in the legislative, regulatory and procedural frameworks related to the prevention and detection of food fraud. These include gaps and ambiguities in definitions, parameters and procedures; limitations in analytical methods and their validation; lack of harmonisation of detection standards; inadequate control and enforcement measures; and insufficient transparency in investigations and enforcement actions. In the honey value chain, for example, challenges include controversial regulations on the definition and labelling of honey, insufficiently sensitive methods for detecting adulteration, and a lack of reliable reference data and harmonised protocols, and weak enforcement capacity to ensure compliance with existing standards.
Vulnerabilities related to international trade and market dynamics	These vulnerabilities stem from challenges in the availability and quality of market and trade data, insufficient cooperation and data sharing between countries, and inconsistencies in trade volumes and prices. In global value chains such as honey, reliance on imports introduces complexities due to differences in regulation and enforcement between countries. Price pressure, below-cost pricing and large-scale adulteration further exacerbate vulnerabilities.

amount of energy. (ID 16, representative of farmers and agri-cooperatives)

This testimony provides valuable insights into several pertinent questions, including who benefits from these outdated standards, who holds institutional power and who maintains the status quo despite advances in analysis. It also addresses those who exert influence to

prevent regulatory reform. Furthermore, it illustrates how different countries or producers can operate under different standards and methods, thereby creating significant economic imbalances. The testimony illustrates how practices such as filtering enable adulteration (e.g., mixing with syrup), giving industrial players an advantage in manipulating products while ostensibly remaining compliant. Finally, an emerging topic from the interviews is the tension surrounding technological access and diverging values among value chain actors.

However, as several participants pointed out, regulatory changes alone will not be sufficient without harmonisation of methods for detecting food fraud, increased controls, greater transparency, and effective enforcement measures. Indeed, regulation gaps combine with limitations in analytical methods and decision mechanisms applied to identify suspicious samples. Most participants in the study point to serious analytical gaps and doubt the detection capabilities of official laboratories due to inadequate harmonisation and validation, with rivalries between laboratories exacerbating the situation. Moreover, concerns have been raised about the accessibility and quality of honey databases, particularly due to limited reference data on botanical traits and production regions. Moreover, they highlight method validation as a critical step in establishing the legal credibility of analytical results. Many actors see the recent JRC methodology advancements as an opportunity and would like this to become the standard, which would lead to more control and a clearer enforcement guidance for authorities in all Member States, as this testimony reflects:

...if we really want to take the issue seriously, let's work with the best (methodology) and it should be harmonised. But then it's a political decision. It means we have to invest more money. We have to have a clear discussion with the Member States, with the food control authorities, etc., to bring them up to speed. But they also need to update the methodology, and the industry also needs to be given clear advice that from now on this is the norm, you can't escape it... It's a challenge. (ID 13, representative of consumer protection organisation)

Similarly, the call for harmonised and validated methods reflects the industry user's need for analytical controls that provide legal certainty and accurately reflect product quality, as noted by a packers' association representative:

...in the end we are users and what we always ask for is to be able to work with legal security...in addition to the process, so to speak, of auditing, control, personal relationship and trust, I can make an assessment that the supplier is a company that works correctly and that follows the established processes... Then, in addition, there are the analytical controls and what we want from the business perspective is that those analytical controls that we use to evaluate the quality of the product we buy, we want the methods to be validated, evaluated and agreed at international level, so that the whole chain, including the control part, is harmonised and I know that by using these methods I have the guarantee that what I am buying later will not have a problem and that this really reflects the quality of the product, is what we demand (ID18, representative of packers' association).

Current regulatory changes are also seen as necessary to address inadequate clarity in labelling regarding botanical and geographical origin. Increasing controls, which are currently perceived as low, is also seen as a priority for the sector. Producer and consumer groups are calling for the results of food fraud investigations and laboratory results to be made public, including data on the extent of adulteration, the frequency of controls, the companies involved, and the methods used to detect fraudulent products.

In addition, consumer organisations are pushing for public exposure measures, which involve publicly "naming and shaming" companies implicated in food fraud. From a consumer perspective, exposing non-compliant companies could act as a deterrent to fraudulent practices, as this participant explains:

Even if the quantities are massive, we will never know which brands we should not buy or which number, the number on the package etc... So, this is a major issue and for us, the transparency... So far there is absolutely no risk because there's never really public exposures, there no exposure, no risk in terms of reputation. So, at the end, so far big brands can use the test they want to pretend they check if it is fraudulent or not... (ID 13, representative of consumer protection organisation)

It was also noted that the cross-border nature of fraud complicates the effective enforcement activities of the competent authorities in both EU and non-EU countries, as well as between EU Member States and within the different services of individual Member States. This makes it more difficult to establish effective communication and coordination, and to generate reliable data.

4.3. Vulnerabilities related to international trade and market dynamics

The honey value chain is characterised by a high degree of globalisation due to a high dependence on imported honey. This reliance on imports means that the value chain spans several countries, each with its own regulations, standards and enforcement mechanisms, providing only a partial view of fraud issues, participants reflected. This global nature introduces complexities in terms of cooperation, data quality and data sharing that make the fight against honey fraud challenging but essential, as pointed out by organisations at the European level. In addition to the physical distance from production, experts highlighted two key aspects when assessing vulnerability: transparent analysis of honey volumes and prices. Experts have noted that fraudsters tend to adulterate honey in large quantities due to cost efficiencies involved in adulteration. This is especially effective when dealing with large batches, where small proportions of adulterants can go unnoticed during routine testing. As noted by a representative of farmers and agri-cooperatives, price inconsistencies undoubtedly point to the presence of fraudulent honey and inconsistent and opaque trade dynamics.

When you imagine that (origin of third country removed) honeys come in at €1.50/kg, 54, 56, it depends a little on the time of year and the dollar rate. At €1.50/kg, it's not honey. It can't be. Honey in (Origin of third country) is paid to the beekeeper at \$2/kg to \$3/kg. And that honey has to be harvested, dehumidified, re-mixed, put back on a boat, sent back and arrived in port here in Europe... When you see import volumes rising and export volumes increasing in the same proportion, you can see that there's a problem... even with the little information we have today, just an analysis of volumes, flows, analysing them in relation to weather conditions, we know that honeys produced in such and such a region, it's a system. It's been so dry, it's impossible. It's not a black box. It's an analysis of production volumes, storage volumes and trading volumes... incl. fluctuations in international trade and exchange rates (ID 16, representative of farmers and agri-cooperatives).

This testimony underscores the complexity and opacity of the global honey supply chain, where improbably low import prices suggest economic and logistical manipulation by industrial actors in exporting countries. These actors appear able to reprocess, blend, and repackage honey in ways that allow them to meet basic regulatory thresholds, despite production costs and environmental constraints, such as drought, rendering such export volumes highly questionable. This highlights a fundamental imbalance between local agricultural realities and the mechanisms of globalised trade. Moreover, the testimony points to a disconnect between observable knowledge (e.g., trade flows, production volumes, and weather conditions) and institutional action.

4.4. Social vulnerability

4.4.1. Consequences of food fraud for vulnerable actors

As beekeepers and their associations have observed, small and medium-scale honey producers who adhere to traditional beekeeping

practices invest significant time, labour and financial resources to ensure authentic, natural honey. However, they are at a competitive disadvantage when fraudulent honey, adulterated with sugar syrups or mislabelled as to its botanical or geographical origin, enters the market at lower prices, as reflected in this testimony:

...the local honey producer is the injured party who competes with those honeys of much lower cost and that may be subject to a process of fraud... I think it is also part of the impotence of the system, that is to say, they produce what they have. And then there are the distributors, the cooperatives, but even those who commercialise local honey can play at doing strange things by introducing thousands of low-cost honeys elsewhere. (ID6, representative of local public organisation).

Participants often articulated concerns about fraudulent practices in the honey market using the terms “fraude por debajo” and “fraude por arriba”, which translate as “fraud from below” and “fraud from above”. Small-scale fraud, or fraud from below, involves unauthorised practices by small-scale or informal producers operating outside legal and sanitary frameworks. According to testimonies, these individuals often present themselves as beekeepers or local producers selling artisanal honey. However, the honey they sell is often of unknown origin, repackaged without regulatory oversight and marketed directly to consumers as high-quality, locally produced honey. They typically bypass required procedures such as honey analysis, health and hygiene inspections, proper labelling and traceability. One common example is individuals keeping more hives than is legally permitted for personal use and selling unlabelled honey without any official control. Small-scale regional honey producers are particularly concerned about the significant quantities of honey produced at the regional level that are being marketed without labels and compliance with minimum standards, while competing directly with their market segment. Adulteration of origin is also a significant concern of regional honey producers due to the lack of exhaustive monitoring of traceability.

On the other hand, “fraud from above” refers to practices attributed to large-scale actors or companies operating within the formal commercial circuit. This includes importing and selling honey from foreign sources under misleading or non-transparent conditions. According to participants, some major players no longer purchase honey in bulk from local producers, but instead import large volumes of honey, often of questionable or undisclosed origin. These imported products may be relabelled or blended without clearly indicating their provenance, misleading consumers into believing they are purchasing domestic or higher-quality honey.

Honey packers who prioritize authenticity face significant challenges due to the adulteration of honey with exogenous sugars. These packers, who seek to pay “fair” prices to producers for high quality honey, feel threatened by the widespread availability of “cheap”, fraudulent products that undermine their market and make it difficult for them to compete on price while maintaining quality standards.

Moreover, several beekeepers highlighted trust as a key deciding factor related to fair trade relations among value chain actors. Honey producers often face pressure to sell their products without full transparency about their final destination or use (mixture), highlighting the vulnerability of actors with limited bargaining power. This dynamic particularly affects producers who require immediate liquidity, forcing them into transactions despite limited trust in their trading partners, as observed in the following testimony:

Trust is given, especially among those beekeepers who sell to other beekeepers who are packers... in the sense that they buy my honey at a price that I understand is reasonable. I know that they are not going to mix it with anything that is not honey from other beekeepers, I know that they are going to fight for that product, but small packers are few in the value chain. And in fact, we know, the industrial operations are much worse in terms of price and it's 'take it or leave it'... and there is no way to negotiate. (ID 12, representative of producer associations)

Several participants in the study reported losses in market share. Although demand for honey is reportedly increasing, many beekeepers face reduced demand from local buyers and a lack of price information, as observed by a honey producer and packer.

...until last year, honey was sold in bulk. You can't compete with these people or you start denouncing everybody or you can't compete and in bulk, because last year there was a brutal price drop, you couldn't sell the honey like that because then you were throwing your money away. Because, of course, it is not only selling the honey, but you have to make money for expenses. And all the warehouses in Spain were saturated with honey. Everybody had honey, there was nowhere to sell the honey and then you realize that there are barrels that are not from Spain. (ID17, honey producer and packer)

Furthermore, value chain actors are concerned about the wider impact of honey fraud on the beekeeping industry. They highlight two key issues: reputational damage to the sector when fraud is uncovered and market distortion from low-priced imports, which makes it challenging for legitimate producers to set and maintain margins that make beekeeping viable and sustainable. Some participants referred to the need for “fair” prices, meaning prices that not only cover costs and provide a reasonable profit (cost-based pricing), but also reward the high quality of the product (value-based pricing). These distortions, as participants pointed out, may also skew consumers’ perception of honey’s true value.

Participants stressed that failure to address fraud not only threatens the economic viability of beekeeping but also puts the cultural heritage and environmental services associated with traditional beekeeping at risk. Participants also emphasised the importance of understanding the socio-ecological dynamics and the implications of food fraud on social and environmental systems. For instance, the sector expects production to fall sharply, which could put many independent beekeepers at risk of going out of business. This would have serious social and environmental consequences, such as reduced pollination services.

4.4.2. Responsibilities and participation in food fraud prevention and detection

A number of actors were mentioned with regard to their responsibilities in preventing and addressing food fraud. As mentioned by the participants in this study, the responsibility of retailers in terms of their pricing and sourcing strategies can have a significant impact on the market and the prevalence of food fraud. For example, low prices for private label honey that do not cover production costs and overlook the risks of supply fluctuations caused by environmental factors affecting beekeeping, can pressure suppliers to cut costs through unethical means, such as adulterating honey with cheaper ingredients like sugar syrups. In addition, several organisations, such as producer and consumer protection organisations, have raised concerns about the responsibilities of private and official laboratories, in order to increase confidence in food fraud detection, which is currently low due to limited analytical methods.

Participants also highlighted that some food business operators deliberately fail, or are unable, to fulfil their core responsibilities in relation to the prevention and detection of food fraud. Similarly, they underlined the responsibility of national authorities to protect consumers and enable them to make informed consumption decisions by providing clear and transparent information. They also stressed the need to strengthen the means of public control of honey on the ground. This includes transparency in investigations and appropriate and public sanctions, as observed by a consumer protection organisation representative:

There is no public consequence. And that's the problem, at some point the decision makers have to decide who they want to protect, business or the citizens, what's in the public interest and the beekeepers of course are also asking for help. Yet, the [fraudulent] products are put on the market, so

it's really a problem... It's completely un-transparent. It's been, it's a very lucrative market. People want to know, and they consider they deserve to know. (ID 13, representative of consumer protection organisation)

While regulators and producers have important responsibilities, participants underlined that consumer awareness plays a crucial role in preventing food fraud, for example, by avoiding suspiciously cheap products.

As participants noted, although fraud in honey has always existed, concerns about the extent and severity of food fraud in the sector have been raised for several decades, particularly by producer and consumer protection organisations. Nevertheless, the sector has received little attention in terms of food fraud control, due to the low health risks associated with the product, limited resources, and methodological limitations of food control authorities, as reflected in the following testimony:

Most stores and establishments don't ask for anything at all. The good thing about it, the good or the bad thing... is that the risk of contamination of honey in a natural way is very low, honey by itself is very stable under normal conditions, this risk is practically minimal. So, what happens, then, that the rest of the tests that the trader or the seller could require, for example, in terms of fraud, of sugars mixed, requires some analysis that neither the buyer is willing to pay nor the seller... That is why I say that the controls that are made are very basic and very scarce ... the ability to discover the fraud is complex. It's very difficult. (ID 10, veterinary, beekeeper and packer)

...because you see honey doesn't expire, it doesn't spoil...everybody is more tolerant, but still, it is not fair for those of us who want to work legally. (ID 08, beekeeper and packer)

Concerning participation and equity in decision making, the European beekeeping sector is perceived as relatively small and less organised than other agricultural sectors. In this context, the limited effective participation in decision-making compared to other agricultural sectors was highlighted, particularly the lower representation of beekeepers compared to other interest groups such as large packers. This perceived lack of influence has made it difficult for beekeepers and honey producers to advocate for stronger regulations that would better protect the integrity of honey and combat food fraud.

well, the sectorial representatives of the beekeeping sector, most of them are the packers. So, we are, so to speak, sending the wolf to look after the flock, we know that they are not going to demand more controls, because well... So, it could be improved if the representatives before the administration were the producers. And not the packers... (ID 10, representative of medium-scale honey producer company).

In response, some actors call for stronger advocacy and greater representation of European honey producers in regulatory bodies and committees dealing with food fraud prevention. Moreover, they demand commitment from policymakers to protect European honey producers from perceived “unfair” trading practices, while maintaining consumer trust in honey products. Further, several adaptation and remedial measures were also raised, as the next section shows.

4.4.3. Adaptations/remedies suggestions

As study participants noted, GI and quality schemes are seen as a way to contribute both to the prevention of food fraud and to risk reduction. Participants marketing honey certified with GI designation, such as protected geographical indication (PGI), reflected on their motivation for certification, which includes protecting their product’s authenticity in terms of botanical and geographical origin and production process, ensuring that the information reaching the consumer is trustworthy and adds value to the product. As noted, without effective control mechanisms, beekeepers are motivated to participate in these schemes to protect their product and way of life, and ultimately their livelihoods.

...I firmly believe that fraud would be avoided a lot, based on the promotion of quality brands, the value of the product from the origin, the knowledge of that product, where it comes from, how expensive it can be to produce it and in the end the quality. (ID 08, beekeeper)

However, questions are raised regarding who should bear the cost of food fraud prevention, as costs are currently incurred by the producer and packaging sectors with no clear price compensation. Sector representatives advocate for clearer labelling systems at EU level, as part of the current food fraud measures within the EU legislation. Moreover, many associations are committed to fostering direct producer–consumer interactions, developing short food supply chains for locally produced honey, and direct sales towards “breaking away from the industrial chains” as explained by this producer association representative:

it is impossible to compete with that, we have recently done an update, a cost study with our farms, our people and we have obtained some data, which is that it is incompatible with profitability, that is why we are constantly calling people who are in our sector to get out of the chain, directly, in the sense that they take charge of the marketing of their own product. Direct sales... in our organisation there is also a lot of committed beekeepers who have small packaging plants and who buy from other beekeepers. So, it doesn't mean that each beekeeper has to do it directly, or that they are encouraged to make direct sales, but rather that maybe they sell to another one who is in their area and who they know sells their own honey, the beekeeper next door who values the product. Because we are more or less clear that the industry and distribution are not our allies... (ID12, representative of producer associations)

As participants reflected, shorter chains could enable a more even distribution of bargaining power among levels. For instance, producers could retain a greater share of the product's market value, by eliminating intermediaries, allowing closer trust relations between chain actors, while increasing traceability.

5. Discussion

5.1. Social vulnerability in the honey value chain

Through narrative analysis, we identify four interrelated levels of food fraud vulnerability in the honey value chain: social vulnerability; product and supply chain-related vulnerabilities; institutional vulnerabilities; and vulnerabilities related to international trade and market dynamics. We place particular emphasis on the importance of social vulnerability factors, such as participation, equity in decision-making, and equity in responsibilities and the distribution of risks and consequences of fraud throughout the food value chain.

This discussion will focus on the analysis of social vulnerability factors. Here, social vulnerability is understood as the socio-economic, political and environmental conditions that limit certain individuals' or groups' capacity to anticipate, cope with or recover from adverse situations (Cutter et al., 2003; Cutter, 2024; Wisner, 2016). According to this definition, vulnerability is not solely determined by exposure to risk, but is also influenced by the presence or absence of effective protective institutions, such as adequate institutional responses and access to resources (Bergstrand et al., 2015). As Bergstrand et al. (2015) argue, these systemic shortcomings can significantly amplify harm, particularly for those with limited bargaining power, market access or institutional protection. Such conditions are often faced by small-scale beekeepers and independent honey packers when confronted with food fraud.

5.2. Distribution of responsibilities and consequences of food fraud

In a sector where production is dominated by small and medium-scale beekeepers, fraud has been identified as a major challenge to beekeeping viability worldwide (Apimondia, 2019, Fairtrade International, 2023). Effective fraud detection is therefore critical not only to

protect consumers and ensure fair trade, but also to sustain the economic livelihood of EU beekeepers (Bruneau et al., 2025). Our study reveals that legitimate, honest producers and packers are directly affected by the illegal activity of food fraudsters, who generate illicit profits and foster unfair competition, ultimately distorting market values and dynamics. Many beekeepers face reduced demand from local buyers and inadequate pricing transparency. Market analysis by Bruneau et al., (2025) confirms these results with findings that European beekeepers selling honey in bulk are struggling to sell their products, or can only do so at unsustainable prices. Key factors include excessive imports of low-priced honey (some of which is adulterated or non-compliant with EU standards), rising EU production costs, market oversupply, and declining consumer demand (Bruneau et al., 2025). Participants described these market dynamics through the lens of competitiveness, emphasising that competitive pressures, exacerbated by market consolidation and price competition, disproportionately harm smaller, more vulnerable actors, particularly when coupled with the availability of lower-priced, fraudulent or mislabelled honey. These actors are limited in their ability to compete on price due to their higher production and distribution costs. In this context, they distinguished between “fraude por debajo” (fraud from below), which refers to fraudulent practices by small-scale or informal actors operating beyond regulatory frameworks, and “fraude por arriba” (fraud from above), which refers to deceptive importation and mislabelling practices by larger, formal-sector companies. Although the underlying motivations differ, both types of fraud are enabled and reinforced by the same structural conditions of competitiveness. For smaller actors, fraud may be a means of short-term survival, whereas for larger actors it is a strategy to protect or expand market share, reduce input costs or circumvent regulation (Lord et al., 2017). The production of fraudulent honey, which often breaches internationally accepted definitions, creates market oversupply, drives prices to unsustainable levels and erodes the value of authentic honey (Bruneau et al., 2025). These distortions generate ‘unfair competition’ with which legitimate producers and packers cannot compete without compromising their integrity, which threatens the long-term viability of beekeeping (Apimondia, 2019).

Moreover, study participants highlighted that food fraud further exacerbates existing power imbalances within the value chain. These include limited participation in decision-making processes, low bargaining power, asymmetric information and structural inequities. These dynamics undermine trust between actors in the value chain and contribute to broader systemic vulnerabilities. From a criminological perspective, research on food fraud suggests that those at the top of the distribution chain hold the most structural power (Huisman & van Ruth, 2022). As a result, as Huisman & van Ruth (2022) discuss, pressures and constraints are largely passed down the chain, influencing the likelihood of fraud.

These imbalances manifest in the form of unfair trading practices (UTPs), which are defined “as business-to-business behaviours that deviate from good commercial conduct and violate principles of good faith and fair dealing” (European Union, 2023b). The food supply chain is particularly susceptible to UTPs due to pronounced power asymmetries between small and large operators (European Union, 2023b). Farmers and small-scale actors lacking sufficient bargaining power often struggle to cope with and protect themselves from these practices, a challenge specifically addressed by Directive (EU) 2019/633 (European Union, 2023b).

Study participants highlighted a particular manifestation of these dynamics: the pressure honey producers face to sell their products without full transparency regarding their final use or destination. This is particularly pertinent in cases where the honey may later be mixed, relabelled, or blended. This lack of transparency reflects the vulnerability of producers who have little influence in commercial negotiations. Those requiring immediate liquidity, such as small-scale or financially constrained beekeepers, may be compelled to accept opaque transactions, despite having little trust in their trading partners. These

circumstances highlight the intersection of economic insecurity and structural inequity, which reinforces producers' exposure to exploitative practices and limits their ability to resist or report potential fraud. In addition to these structural imbalances, a further challenge lies in the unequal capacity of different actors, especially small vs. large enterprises, to implement effective food fraud mitigation. As Popping et al. (2022) highlight, much globally recognized guidance for food authenticity management (such as FSSC 22000, IFS, or BRCGS) requires extensive documentation, supplier audits, and analytical verification, resources typically more accessible to large enterprises. Small-scale and independent producers and packers often lack the infrastructure to engage with such requirements, leaving them more vulnerable to fraudulent practices within the value chain.

These structural limitations not only expose small producers and packers to heightened fraud risks but also contribute to broader shifts in power across the value chain. One such shift, driven by increasing concerns over authenticity and control, is particularly evident in the Aotearoa New Zealand manuka honey sector. Research by Finlay-Smits et al. (2023) suggests that increasing threats have altered the power dynamics between actors in the value chain. In response to the growing demand for authenticity, control has shifted away from beekeepers and honey companies to landowners, who seek transparency and fair compensation, and to consumers, who increasingly prioritise product quality, provenance, and authenticity, as well as the ethics of the associated practices (Finlay-Smits et al., 2023).

The narratives presented in this study also frame the issue of responsibility for preventing food fraud. As some of participants noted, certain food business operators either intentionally neglect or are unable to fulfil their key responsibilities in preventing and detecting food fraud. Similarly, forensic investigations carried out by Member States and OLAF, including on-site inspections, sampling and examination of digital records, have revealed collusion between exporters and importers involved in various honey adulteration practices (European Union, 2023a). These practices include diluting honey with sugar syrups to reduce costs in both EU and non-EU markets, using accredited laboratory analyses to manipulate honey/sugar blends to avoid detection by clients and authorities before import, adding additives and colourings to alter the perceived botanical origin of honey, and falsifying traceability data or removing pollen to obscure the true geographical origin of honey (European Union, 2023a).

Participants also highlighted that retailers' pricing and sourcing strategies can significantly impact the market and the prevalence of food fraud. They highlighted a similar trend to that noted by the EU Pollinator Hub: retailers are aggressively pushing for lower prices. While this may benefit consumers, it has a severe impact on EU beekeepers, who are contending with rising production costs (Bruneau et al., 2025). This issue is especially relevant given that around 80 percent of imported honey is used in blends and sold under different brand names (European Federation of Honey Packers and Distributors, FEEDM, cited in European Union, 2023a). In addition, the widespread availability of fraudulent, low-priced honey products on the market, coupled with poor transparency in the honey value chain, could have a significant negative impact on consumers' perception of the real value of honey, as highlighted by study participants. When consumers encounter deceptively cheap honey that may have been adulterated with sugar syrups or mislabelled, their trust in the authenticity and quality of genuine honey may be undermined. This could diminish the perceived value of honey as a premium, natural product, creating reputational damage for the whole sector. However, the impact of food fraud on product valuation is an emerging area of research (see e.g., Barbarossa, 2018). For example, a recent study on the valuation of US honey shows that improvements in fraud detection technologies may have the effect of increasing consumers' perceived differentiation between products of different origins and their willingness to pay for domestically produced honey (Gustafson et al., 2024). However, in the aftermath of past food fraud incidents, efforts to demonstrate product authenticity, enhance supply chain

security, and ensure compliance with product and process standards are costly (Ehmke et al., 2019). These increased costs are likely to raise the price of products vulnerable to fraud over time (Ehmke et al., 2019), placing an additional burden on honest producers and packers who already face unfair competition.

Additionally, the broader implications of quality uncertainty and ineffective verification mechanisms may drive high-quality suppliers from the market, as illustrated by Akerlof's (1970) 'Market for Lemons' and the adverse selection problem, which explains how markets reliant on trust can deteriorate when buyers cannot distinguish between high- and low-quality products. In the honey value chain, where trust is important, widespread food fraud could lead to the exit of many legitimate small beekeepers and packers from the market. This trend may further undermine the incentive structures for traditional honey-producing countries to maintain the production and export of authentic natural honey (Apimondia, 2019).

Although food fraud is often associated with low-quality producers seeking to gain a price premium through adulteration or mislabelling, evidence from Meerza et al. (2019, 2021) demonstrates that high-quality producers may also engage in fraudulent practices. In particular, they may reduce costs through adulteration or mislabelling without lowering prices, thereby gaining a competitive advantage that is difficult to detect through conventional market signals (Meerza et al., 2019). This insight is particularly relevant to the dynamics described in "fraud from above", where even high-quality producers operating within the formal value chain may engage in deceptive practices, such as misrepresenting the origin or quality of imported honey, in response to competitive pressures, despite their capacity to produce authentic natural honey.

Meerza et al. (2019) further show that producer heterogeneity influences both the likelihood of producers engaging in fraudulent behaviour and being affected by it, with both low- and high-quality producers facing varying incentives depending on social attitudes towards fraudulent behaviour enforcement policy parameters, and the relative magnitude of the demand and supply effects of food fraud. These findings emphasise the importance of acknowledging producer heterogeneity and the varying welfare consequences of food fraud. They challenge preconceived notions about who benefits from food fraud and who is harmed by it, highlighting the necessity of more nuanced food fraud vulnerability assessments.

5.3. Framings of solution and remedial actions

In analysing the responses and remedies as expressed by study participants, we find that direct trade and short supply chains are seen as a way to improve traceability, ensure product authenticity and reduce disparities between large, often multinational, companies and small producers. However, questions remain regarding the scalability of such approaches. Additionally, GI and quality schemes play a role in food fraud prevention by certifying product authenticity and ensuring traceability. As noted by Ehmke et al. (2019), labels and certification are widely adopted in food markets to address issues of asymmetric information. For certified products, the certifying body holds full regulatory authority over whether a product meets its standards. While ethically certified food is inspected for safety, it is unlikely to undergo certification compliance checks at import or transit points (Lindley et al., 2023). As observed by Di Fonzo & Russo (2015), ensuring food quality in GI products involves balancing strict production standards by providing adequate incentives for producers. Rigid controls may discourage participation, while involving diverse producers in GI design is crucial but challenging due to their varying interests.

Transparency considerations highlighted in this study range from the disclosure of data on food fraud and the outcome of official investigations to the public exposure of non-compliant operators ("naming and shaming"). In this context, digital technologies can, in some cases, increase transparency in the context of food fraud prevention. For

instance, in the Aotearoa New Zealand manuka honey value chain, digital technologies have been used to foster trust and demonstrate the integrity and trustworthiness of the value chain actors (Finlay-Smits et al., 2023). However, from a social justice perspective, an important question arises: who should bear the costs of ensuring authenticity and transparency? Study participants highlight concerns that certification efforts may not be justified in terms of price and could disproportionately burden beekeepers. In addition, the increased cost of verification methods raises the price of authenticated products relative to fraudulent ones, with significant welfare implications, particularly for consumers who cannot afford certified products (Ehmke et al., 2019).

Study participants raised concerns about the definition of honey, inconsistencies in labelling standards, and the regulation of processing methods such as filtration, maturation, and dehumidification. These issues are further exacerbated by the use of unreliable authenticity databases and reference data on honey's botanical and geographical origins. Participants also emphasised the urgent need for harmonised detection methods, as well as adequate control and enforcement measures. Studies showing that regulatory gaps are exacerbated by limited analytical capacities and ineffective decision-making processes support these concerns (see e.g., Richardson, 2024; Bruneau et al., 2025). In this context, producer organisations and consumer protection associations viewed the recent advancements in the Joint Research Centre's (JRC) methodology as a step forward, as it offers potential for harmonised standards across the EU that would provide both legal clarity and practical utility for market operators and regulators alike. However, harmonised and widely accepted analytical methods are still needed to enhance official laboratories' abilities to detect honey that has been adulterated with custom-made sugar syrups that closely replicate the sugar profile of genuine honey (Ždiniaková et al., 2023; European Union, 2024b). Likewise, Bruneau et al. (2025) recommend that, to effectively protect against and combat honey fraud, the EU must adopt harmonised, officially recognised analytical methods, together with rapid, robust enforcement supported by a shared database of authentic honey. Existing techniques should be continuously improved while new methods are tested and integrated into the official toolkit (Bruneau et al., 2025).

However, as participants pointed out, efforts to combat fraud risk will fall short and increase the exposure of already vulnerable actors, such as legitimate and honest producers and packers, unless deeper systemic, institutional, and methodological vulnerabilities are addressed.

5.4. Comparative vulnerability assessments and future research directions

Comparative vulnerability assessments using the SSAFE tool across various supply chains, (e.g., fish, meat, milk, olive oil, organic bananas, and spices) highlight significant variations in vulnerability levels across tiers (van Ruth et al., 2018). Van Ruth et al. (2018) found that wholesalers are considered the most vulnerable group, followed by retailers, and processors. However, primary producers, such as farmers and fishermen, were not included in the study. The study highlighted technical and managerial gaps, particularly the limited presence of managerial (soft) controls such as social norms, food policy enforcement, and broader environmental-level deterrents. Importantly, and consistent with our findings, food fraud vulnerability was shown to be determined by both the commodity chain and the actor's position within the chain. Another study examining fraud vulnerability across organic food supply chains (banana, egg, olive oil and pork) found that the organic chains appeared slightly less vulnerable than conventional chains due to fewer opportunities for fraud and more adequate controls (van Ruth & de Pagter-de Witte, 2020). However, these chains were associated with enhanced vulnerability resulting from (business) cultural and behavioural drivers. Here again processors and wholesale were assessed for their fraud vulnerabilities, but primary producers and retailers were not included (van Ruth & de Pagter-de Witte, 2020). Notably, in the context

of culture and behaviour, the authors distinguish between vulnerability as a susceptibility to external threats and an increased risk of becoming a victim of food fraud, and vulnerability arising from threats within a group's own company (van Ruth & de Pagter-de Witte, 2020). Further assessment of these studies concludes that food fraud vulnerability assessment tools measure perceived food fraud vulnerabilities by food businesses; however, conclusions about actual prevalence and underlying causal factors cannot be deducted from the outcomes of their use (Huisman & van Ruth, 2022).

In a way that we see complementary to these studies, our findings emphasise the centrality of social vulnerability and power imbalances as primary factors influencing fraud risk, particularly for small-scale beekeepers and honey packers. While technical detection capacities, managerial controls, and recent regulatory changes are essential components of fraud prevention, this study highlights that in fragmented sectors like honey, where many actors operate with low institutional support and limited market power, addressing socio-economic inequities and structural marginalisation is equally important. Elements such as trust, fairness and transparency should be seen as complementary in efforts to effectively tackle the ongoing crisis in the sector. As Asomah & Cheng (2018) argue, the culture of fraud is driven by commercial profit motives that often outweigh collective interests, including consumer welfare. One participant highlighted this tension, stating "... at some point the decision-makers have to decide who they want to protect, business or citizens, what's in the public interest? And of course the beekeepers are also asking for help". Popping et al. (2022) note that the relationship between the food industry and regulators in the context of food fraud is complex and frequently strained; while the industry seeks protection from illegal influence of food fraud, it also demands the freedom to trade without undue restriction. This inherent tension has shifted over time, often shaped by the broader global political landscape (Popping et al., 2022). Gray (2018, p. 414) similarly observes that the modern global food system, dominated by industrial corporations, operates as a "risky food regime" in which food crimes and harms are considered "normal probability-based" outcomes of systemic conditions. Food fraud is shaped by context-specific conditions, such as supply, demand, regulation, and competition, which vary according to the geo-historical, political, economic, and social environments in which it occurs (Lord et al. 2017). This highlights the need to address the underlying political and socio-economic factors that increase the vulnerability of the food system and its actors to food fraud. These structures also determine who is disproportionately affected by fraudulent practices, emphasising the limitations of relying solely on narrow regulatory measures. Future research should investigate how the vulnerability levels identified in this study (see Table 2), are constituted in different agri-food supply chains, and how they interact with factors such as scale, regulatory complexity, and value chain structure to influence food fraud vulnerability. Such comparative studies are crucial for informing equitable policy responses.

5.5. Contribution to the international food policy debate

In line with calls for advancing just transitions in the European food system, we highlight the importance of studying social vulnerabilities related to food fraud and the need to prioritise them in the European food fraud policy framework. As outlined in the Farm to Fork Strategy, ensuring a sustainable livelihood for primary producers, who still lag behind in terms of income, and capturing a fair share of the added value of sustainable production, is essential for the success of the agri-food transition, while ensuring that social rights are respected for all actors in the value chain (European Union, 2020). An explicit inclusion of social vulnerability in the legislative agenda on food fraud would require an extension of current measures to focus on fair trading practices, minimum prices and transparent contracting systems that can reduce the risk of fraud by more powerful actors in the value chain, as set out in the EU Directive on Unfair Trading Practices in the Agricultural

and Food Supply Chain (European Union, 2019). Acknowledging the importance of social vulnerability requires that food fraud vulnerability assessments account for factors such as participation and equity in decision-making, fair distribution of responsibilities and risks, and impacts across the value chain, while also considering the wider environmental impacts of food fraud. As Meerza et al. (2019) observed, policy responses should move beyond simple quality-based distinctions and instead account for actor heterogeneity and the differentiated welfare effects of food fraud across the supply chain. Following the concept of social vulnerability, this article proposes a framework that places vulnerable actors, such as small-scale producers, independent packers, and those with limited institutional support, at the centre of food fraud vulnerability assessments, by linking regulatory gaps with social, economic, and institutional factors that constrain their ability to prevent, respond to, or recover from fraud.

In view of the negative consequences of food fraud, organisations like Copa-Cogeca stress the need for the Commission to launch promotion programmes for European honey through the policy envelope for market disturbances and have encouraged Member States to include measures such as support for investment in beekeeping in their future CAP strategic plans and national apiculture programmes (Copa-Cogeca, 2020, see also European Commission, 2024b).

Our assessment of vulnerabilities related to international trade and market dynamics shows that price pressures and opaque trade and market dynamics, alongside large-scale adulteration practices, exacerbate social vulnerability. Bruneau et al. (2025) recommend establishing transparent EU-level market regulation tools, such as market indexes, to guide investors and assist supply chain participants in adapting. Furthermore, Member States should promptly provide up-to-date statistical data on honey consumption and trade analysis (Bruneau et al., 2025). This underlines the need for greater transparency of trade data, robust plausibility analysis, early warning systems and enhanced international cooperation to effectively combat food fraud. An additional challenge is the limited sharing of relevant data and intelligence between industry stakeholders and competent authorities (Siligato et al., 2024). Initiatives like the Food Industry Intelligence Network (FIIN) show progress by enabling confidential, anonymised data sharing and joint intelligence gathering through an independent body (Food Authenticity Network, n.d.). In particular, economic stakeholders stand to benefit from mutual information exchange; however, achieving this requires significant investment in computing infrastructure and skilled personnel to modernise the EU's current IT landscape (Siligato et al., 2024).

Although recent EU regulatory developments and international cooperation initiatives have aimed to improve the detection and prevention of honey adulteration and other types of food fraud, the extent to which they address structural inequalities and reduce fraud-related risks among different groups remains unclear. It is therefore necessary to assess these initiatives, particularly to understand how new technological, methodological and legislative measures may support or inadvertently affect vulnerable groups.

Finally, it must be noted that social and biophysical vulnerability are linked and should be treated accordingly (Turner et al., 2003). For example, for communities with strong cultural ties to traditional beekeeping, food fraud can undermine cultural heritage and identity by disrespecting traditional practices and knowledge. Furthermore, failure to protect traditional beekeeping can have serious implications for environmental sustainability by disrupting a range of environmental services like pollination (Apimondia, 2019).

6. Conclusion

Our study advances the conceptual understanding of food fraud vulnerability by integrating the concept of social vulnerability and highlighting its multi-level structure. We identify various levels of food fraud vulnerability, including product- and supply chain-related

vulnerabilities, institutional vulnerabilities, and vulnerabilities related to international trade and market dynamics. These nested levels of vulnerability reinforce and exacerbate social vulnerability, particularly for the most vulnerable actors in the value chain. This study underscores the importance of understanding the conditions, both within the chain and in the broader structural, environmental, social, and political contexts that exacerbate and perpetuate this vulnerability.

To that end we advocate for the integration of social vulnerability factors, such as participation, equity in decision-making and fair distribution of risks, consequences and responsibilities in preventing food fraud, into both food fraud vulnerability assessments and regulatory frameworks.

Addressing food fraud effectively requires legislative and policy measures that prioritise the protection of vulnerable actors, enhance transparency, enforce fair trading practices, and protect consumer rights.

Future research should investigate how social vulnerability is constructed across different agri-food value chains, and how it interacts with factors such as scale, regulatory complexity, and value chain structure to shape food fraud vulnerability. Embedding social vulnerability at the core of both analytical and legislative agendas is critical to achieving important social objectives of European food policy.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Claudia Coral: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Dagmar Mithöfer:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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